

APPLICATION OF THE AGILE METHODOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF HYBRID PROJECT TEAMS IN THE MARITIME INDUSTRY**Sherstiuk O.***Candidate of Engineering Sciences,
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Odesa, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115128>**Abstract**

This paper explores the formation and management of hybrid project teams in the maritime industry, emphasising the interaction between onboard, shore-based, and remote personnel. The study examines the potential of the Agile methodology in optimising hybrid team management by enhancing flexibility, communication, and decision-making processes. Agile principles, such as iterative planning and continuous feedback, are analysed in maritime operations, where traditional hierarchical structures often prevail. A conceptual model for structuring hybrid teams is proposed, covering key stages such as defining project requirements, selecting team members, assigning roles and responsibilities, establishing communication frameworks, managing risks, and evaluating performance. This model aims to improve coordination and adaptability within hybrid teams, ensuring efficient collaboration across different operational environments. A mathematical model is introduced to optimise team formation while considering budget, time, and personnel competencies constraints. By integrating Agile principles with optimisation techniques, the model ensures a balanced allocation of resources, minimises operational risks and enhances overall project efficiency. The findings contribute to improving hybrid team management in the maritime industry by offering structured approaches to team formation and project execution. The proposed models provide practical insights for maritime organisations seeking to enhance workforce efficiency, streamline operations, and adapt to evolving industry challenges.

Keywords: hybrid project teams, maritime industry, Agile methodology, team management, resource optimisation, onboard and shore-based personnel, risk management, communication frameworks.

Introduction. The modern world is in constant motion, and the maritime industry, one of the economy's most globalised and technologically complex sectors, is no exception. The COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, and the economic and environmental challenges of recent years have significantly affected the work organisation in this industry. In particular, growing instability, the need to adapt to new conditions, and increased resilience to external factors have forced companies to seek innovative project and team management approaches. One such approach is the formation of hybrid teams that combine local and remote workers. Hybrid teams have become not just a temporary solution in response to the restrictions associated with the pandemic, war, and other socio-economic and political problems but a new reality that allows companies to use resources effectively, attract the best specialists regardless of their geographical location, and increase productivity. Hybrid teams are becoming particularly relevant in the maritime industry, where projects are often multifunctional and interdisciplinary and require high coordination between participants. They allow experts from different fields, such as maritime logistics, engineering, ecology, finance and information technology, to be brought together to solve complex tasks. However, the formation and management of hybrid teams in the maritime industry have their characteristics. Unlike traditional teams, hybrid teams require new approaches to communication, knowledge management, motivation and distribution of responsibilities. In addition, an important aspect is ensuring a balance between local and remote employees and minimising the risks associated with a fragmented work

environment. One of the most promising approaches to forming and managing hybrid teams is the Agile methodology, which is based on flexibility, self-organisation and continuous improvement. Agile allows teams to respond quickly to changes, effectively allocate resources and ensure high-quality project implementation. However, despite the widespread use of Agile in various industries, its application in the maritime sector remains underexplored, especially in the context of forming hybrid teams.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The issues of forming and managing hybrid teams have been studied by many scientists and practitioners. In particular, the research in [1] emphasises the importance of adaptability in managing innovative projects in a BANI environment (Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear, Incomprehensible). The authors point out the need for flexible approaches to team management that allow for rapid adaptation to change and uncertainty.

The paper [2] examines the interaction between people and autonomous systems in hybrid teams. The authors emphasise that effective communication and trust are key factors for success in such teams. These findings are especially relevant for the maritime industry, where autonomous technologies, such as unmanned vessels, are becoming increasingly widespread.

The research in [3] is devoted to the economic and mathematical modelling of team formation processes. The authors propose approaches to optimising the allocation of resources and tasks in teams, which is essential for the maritime industry, where resources are often limited and tasks are complex and multifactorial.

In the context of project management methodologies, the authors in [4] consider a hybrid approach that combines traditional (Waterfall) and flexible (Agile) methods. This approach benefits the maritime industry, where some projects have clearly defined requirements while others require flexibility and adaptation to changes.

However, these works do not highlight the specifics of forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry; in particular, they do not take into account the high level of technical complexity of projects, the need for coordination between different departments (logistics, engineering, ecology) and work in remote conditions (on ships, offshore platforms, etc.), and also do not sufficiently reflect the application of the Agile methodology in the maritime industry, in particular in the context of hybrid teams, where flexibility, self-organisation and continuous improvement are key success factors. This determines the relevance of this study, which is aimed at filling these gaps and integrating Agile approaches into forming hybrid teams for the maritime industry.

The aim of the research is to develop a model for forming hybrid teams for the maritime industry using the Agile methodology, which allows for optimising project management processes, ensuring effective communication between team members, and adapting to changes in dynamic conditions.

The objectives of the article are:

1. To analyse the features of the functioning of hybrid teams in the maritime industry, particularly the interaction of onboard, shore-based, and remote personnel.
2. To investigate the basic principles of the Agile methodology and the possibilities of its application for managing hybrid teams in the maritime sector.
3. To develop a conceptual model for forming hybrid teams, including defining project requirements, selecting participants, assigning roles and responsibilities, creating a communication structure, managing risks, and assessing effectiveness.
4. To propose a mathematical model for optimising the process of forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry, considering budget, time, and competency constraints integrated with Agile principles.

Materials of the research. Hybrid teams in the maritime industry are a unique organisational structure

that combines onboard, shore-based and remote personnel. Their functioning is based on close interaction between all participants in the shipping process and the use of modern digital technologies to ensure the smooth operation of the fleet.

Onboard personnel working directly on the vessel are primarily responsible for the ship's safety, navigation and technical condition. The captain coordinates the crew's work, makes strategic decisions, and communicates with shore services. Navigators are responsible for navigation, route planning, and course corrections in accordance with weather conditions and shipping situations. Mechanical engineers ensure the operability of the main and auxiliary mechanisms of the vessel, and communication operators support communication with the external environment. Shore-based personnel play an essential role in the strategic and operational management of the fleet. Fleet managers control routes, plan and allocate resources, dispatchers monitor vessel movements, weather conditions and potential risks, and analysts calculate flight efficiency, fuel consumption and route cost-effectiveness. Security specialists develop emergency protocols and conduct threat assessments.

Remote personnel include specialists who perform support functions and provide expert support to shipping companies. IT specialists provide technical support for digital platforms, consultants develop environmental standards and operational solutions recommendations, and cybersecurity analysts protect shipping systems from potential attacks [5].

The coordinated work of hybrid teams is based on using advanced technologies. Satellite communication systems such as VSAT and Inmarsat ensure an uninterrupted exchange of information between the crew and shore services. Cloud platforms and ERP systems facilitate centralised data management, while IoT solutions allow real-time monitoring of machinery status, weather conditions, and resource consumption. Artificial intelligence and big data are used to analyse navigation information, predict risks, and automate decision-making processes.

Despite all the advantages, the operation of hybrid teams comes with several challenges (Table 1).

Table 1

Key challenges in the functioning of hybrid teams in the maritime industry and ways to solve them

Challenge	Solution
Unstable connection in the open sea	Using backup communication channels and autonomous IT solutions.
Time zones	Flexible meeting schedule and asynchronous communication.
Cultural differences	Conducting trainings on cross-cultural interaction.
Technical malfunctions	Automated diagnostic systems and remote maintenance.
Cyber threats	Implementation of cybersecurity systems, multi-level authentication.

One of the main problems is unstable communication in the open sea, which can lead to delays in decision-making. Backup communication channels and autonomous control systems are used to minimise this risk. Another difficulty may be the difference in time

zones between team members, which makes it difficult to synchronise work processes. This is solved by using a flexible communication schedule and the use of asynchronous methods of information exchange.

In addition, the multinational composition of teams requires considering cultural differences, which can affect the effectiveness of interaction. Specialised training in cross-cultural communication is organised to eliminate this barrier. Technical malfunctions on board the vessel can complicate the crew's work, but remote diagnostics and support systems allow for promptly resolving such problems. At the same time, cyber threats remain a serious challenge, requiring the implementation of multi-level security systems, including data encryption and multi-factor authentication.

Thus, the functioning of hybrid teams in the maritime industry is based on the interaction between onboard, shore-based and remote personnel, their effective use of digital technologies and clear regulation of processes. This approach allows for the optimised management of shipping operations, increased safety, and the assurance of flexibility and adaptability in the dynamic conditions of the modern maritime environment.

Managing hybrid teams in the maritime industry requires effective interaction between onboard, shore-based and remote personnel and the ability to adapt to changes quickly, optimise work processes and ensure high decision-making efficiency. These requirements make the Agile methodology one of the most promising approaches to organising the work of hybrid teams in the maritime sector. Flexible management allows the implementation of an iterative approach, improves communication between process participants and effectively responds to external challenges [6]. For the maritime industry, the following main principles of the Agile methodology can be distinguished:

1. Adaptability to changes in the marine environment. Flexible management allows for rapid response to changing weather conditions, port delays, regulatory changes, and other unforeseen factors.

2. Iterative planning of maritime operations. Shipping companies can divide large tasks (voyages, maintenance, cargo transportation) into short cycles (sprints), constantly adjusting routes, technical procedures, and logistical processes.

3. Flexible interaction between onboard, shore-based, and remote personnel. The use of daily online meetings (stand-ups), clear digital communication, and transparent information exchange between crew, dispatchers, and technical specialists allows for rapid decision-making.

4. Autonomy and self-organisation of teams. Hybrid team members have the ability to make decisions independently within their competence, which reduces dependence on centralised management and speeds up work processes.

5. Transparency in shipping processes. Regular data updates on flights, vessel status, cargo and crew allow all participants to receive up-to-date information and avoid errors quickly.

6. Continuous improvement of operations. Analysis of completed flights, maintenance, and crew work allows for real-time changes to be implemented and fleet efficiency to be improved.

7. Focus on safety and risk management. Agile allows for flexible adaptation of safety protocols to current threats, considering changing weather conditions, vessel technical conditions, cyberattacks and the human factor.

Implementing these principles in the maritime industry increases fleet management efficiency, reduces costs, and minimises risks in a dynamic shipping environment. The use of the Agile methodology in the formation of hybrid teams allows not only to increase their adaptability but also to optimise the processes of organising work, distributing roles and ensuring effective communication between all participants. Implementing flexible management principles allows you to create a conceptual model of a hybrid team based on a phased approach, a clear interaction structure, and the use of digital technologies to coordinate activities. Such a model contributes to the effective implementation of shipping operations, minimises risks and ensures prompt decision-making in changing conditions of the maritime environment. Thus, for the effective implementation of the Agile methodology in the maritime industry, it is necessary to develop a conceptual model of the formation of hybrid teams, which takes into account the specifics of shipping operations, a multi-level management structure and the features of interaction between onboard, shore-based and remote personnel. The proposed model is based on the key stages of team organisation, the distribution of roles in accordance with the principles of Agile and the implementation of effective communication mechanisms. A detailed consideration of these aspects allows us to determine the optimal approaches to team management and ensure its flexibility and adaptability in a dynamic maritime environment.

Organising a hybrid team involves structuring processes, distributing roles, and implementing effective communication mechanisms between offline (onboard personnel, port services) and online participants (shore teams, IT department, management). The organisation process takes place in five key stages: defining the goals and objectives of the hybrid team, developing the principles of interaction and communications, defining the work planning process (Sprint Planning), performing tasks in a hybrid environment, analysing results and implementing improvements [7].

Thus, forming a hybrid team in the maritime industry based on the Agile methodology begins with defining key roles and team organisation. At this stage, the goals and tasks that the team must perform are clearly outlined, and its composition is formed. Team members can work directly on the ship, in shore offices or remotely. An important step is the assignment of key roles according to the Agile methodology: the Product Owner sets priorities and manages the task backlog, the Scrum Master ensures compliance with Agile principles and coordinates the team, and the remaining members take on the relevant functional responsibilities [7]. The result of this stage is a clear understanding of the team's roles, responsibilities and goals (Table 2).

Role distribution in a hybrid team

Role	Function	Location
Product Owner	Sets priorities, monitors task execution	Online
Scrum Master	Coordinates the team, holds daily meetings, eliminates obstacles	Online
Vessel Crew	Performs operational tasks, ensures the safety of the vessel	Offline (ship)
Port Operations	Responsible for cargo handling, coordination of ship calls	Offline (port)
Technical Service	Equipment maintenance, repair work	Offline (port/ship)
Shore Team	Analytics, financial planning, monitoring	Online (office)
IT Support	Digital systems support, cybersecurity	Online
Management	Strategic decision-making, financing	Online

In hybrid teams in the maritime industry, the distribution of the Product Owner and Scrum Master roles depends on the company's management structure and the specifics of the operations. The Product Owner is usually a shipping company or fleet operator representative responsible for defining strategic goals, setting priorities and managing the task backlog. This can be:

- 1) Fleet Manager – responsible for vessel maintenance, cost optimisation and operational efficiency.
- 2) Operations Manager – coordinates the interaction between the ship and shore teams.
- 3) Client Manager or ship owner representative – if the operations are performed on behalf of a ship owner or logistics company, the Product Owner may represent their interests.

The Scrum Master is the person who ensures compliance with the Agile methodology, helps remove obstacles in the team's work and supports effective communication. In a maritime environment, this role can be performed by:

- 1) Hybrid Team Coordinator – a manager who supports interaction between all team members.
- 2) Captain of the ship – if the Agile processes concern operations on board a vessel, the Scrum Master may be the captain or senior assistant coordinating the crew's actions.
- 3) Project Manager – if the company is working on large-scale digital or operational changes, the Scrum Master may be a specially appointed specialist.

Thus, depending on the specific project and organisational structure, the roles of Product Owner and Scrum Master can be performed by different officials; the main thing is to define their duties and responsibilities clearly.

The next critical stage is to establish the principles of interaction and communication. Digital tools such as ERP, task tracking, and video communication tools have been implemented to facilitate effective team coordination. The format and frequency of meetings are determined: daily stand-ups to synchronise work, weekly reports, and completed sprint reviews. Unified

protocols for information exchange between ship and shore personnel are also implemented, eliminating possible communication barriers and ensuring coordinated interaction.

After creating the team and establishing communications, the work planning process (Sprint Planning) begins. At this stage, the Product Owner forms a list of priority tasks (backlog), and the team, together with the Scrum Master, discusses their distribution among the participants. It is crucial to balance the load between offline participants (ship crew, port operators, technical personnel) and online participants (managers, IT specialists, analysts). The sprint duration is determined, which for the maritime sector is optimally 2–4 weeks. At the end of this stage, the team receives a clear work plan for the upcoming period.

Then, the implementation of tasks in a hybrid environment begins. Team members work according to the sprint plan: onboard personnel perform operational tasks on the vessel, port services provide logistics, and remote specialists support processes through analytical tools and technical support. Daily stand-ups play an essential role, during which participants report on progress, discuss difficulties and synchronise their actions. This allows for prompt adjustment of processes, ensuring their maximum efficiency.

The final stage is the analysis of results and implementation of improvements. After the sprint, the team conducts a Sprint Review, where the quality of the tasks and compliance with the initial goals are assessed. Then, problems that arose during the work are analysed at the Sprint Retrospective stage, and opportunities for process improvement are identified. Based on the findings, the task backlog is updated, and the team moves to the next sprint, implementing new optimisation solutions.

Thanks to such a structured organisation, the hybrid team becomes more adaptive, efficient, and able to quickly respond to the challenges of the dynamic marine environment (Pic. 1).

Pic. 1 – A conceptual model for forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry based on the Agile methodology

Thus, the proposed conceptual model for forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry based on Agile provides effective management of shipping operations. A clear role structure, an iterative approach to task performance, and flexible communication mechanisms allow for optimisation of the planning, control, and adaptation processes to changes. This model can increase decision-making efficiency through daily meetings, improved coordination between shipboard, shore, and remote personnel, flexibility and adaptability in dynamic shipping conditions, and optimisation of resource allocation and cost reduction. However, despite significant advantages, effective implementation of the model requires overcoming specific challenges, including ensuring reliable communication between all team members, forming an Agile culture among maritime personnel, and integrating digital technologies into traditional management processes.

To achieve maximum efficiency, additional optimisation mechanisms must be implemented. The mathematical model can accurately assess resources, costs, and risks, determining the optimal strategies for each hybrid team in actual shipping conditions. This involves formulating objective functions that maximise task performance and applying constraints considering weather conditions, port congestion, budget constraints, and personnel availability [8].

The objective function for optimising the process of forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry aims to maximise team performance by ensuring balanced resource utilisation, minimising costs, and adapting to changing conditions (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{e \in E} & (w_1 KPI_t - w_2 C_{e,t} - w_3 R_e + w_4 W_t \\
 & - w_5 P_e) x_{e,t} \\
 & + \delta \sum_{e \in E} L_p - \gamma \sum_{t \in T} (1 - F_t) x_{e,t} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ – period set which defines the time frame in which tasks can be performed;

$E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m\}$ – set of all tasks;

$P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k\}$ – set of all team members;

$x_{e,t}$ – binary variable which determines whether task e is being performed at time t (1 – yes, 0 – no);

KPI_t – the importance factor of the task t that must be completed;

$C_{e,t}$ – costs of completing task e for at time t ;

R_e – risk associated with performing task e (for example, delays or emergencies);

W_t – coefficient of weather conditions at the time of task execution t (1 – ideal conditions, 0 – storm);

P_e – port load for task e (1 – full load, 0 – free port);

L_p – engagement level of employee p (the more they work, the higher the productivity);

F_t – task completion factor (1 – done, 0 – not done);

w_1 – KPI significance coefficient of tasks in the overall objective function (the higher the value, the more significant the impact of completing tasks with a high KPI);

w_2 – coefficient of the impact of costs on task performance (the higher the value, the more the model tries to minimise costs);

w_3 – task risk factor (increases or decreases the weight of risks, such as delays or emergencies);

w_4 – coefficient of influence of weather conditions on task performance (with high values, the model will consider the influence of weather on task performance more);

w_5 – coefficient of influence of port load on task completion (if it is high, the system will try to avoid tasks during busy periods);

δ – coefficient that determines the impact of employee engagement on overall efficiency (the higher the value, the more their workload and productivity are considered).

γ – coefficient that determines the degree of importance of task completion in overall planning (with high values, the system will focus more on completing each task).

This model maximises team efficiency, increasing KPIs and employee engagement and minimising costs, risks, and downtime due to bad weather or port delays.

To ensure the safety and efficiency of task performance, restrictions that prohibit or limit the performance of specific tasks during adverse weather conditions are introduced.

$$x_{e,t} \leq W_t, \forall e \in E, \forall t \in T \quad (2)$$

where $x_{e,t}$ – determines whether task e is being performed at time t (1 – yes, 0 – no);

W_t – coefficient of weather conditions at the time of task execution t (1 – ideal conditions, 0 – storm);

If $W_t = 0$, (adverse weather conditions), then $x_{e,t} = 0$, i.e. the task cannot be performed. If $W_t = 1$, the performance is allowed. Such a constraint allows the hybrid team to adapt its work schedule to dynamic changes in the marine environment, ensuring personnel safety and effective task planning.

To avoid port congestion [9] and ensure effective management of shipping operations, we introduce constraints that regulate the number of simultaneous operations in the port.

$$\sum_{t \in T} x_{e,t} P_t \leq P_{max} \quad (3)$$

where $x_{e,t}$ – binary variable which determines whether task e is being performed at time t (1 – yes, 0 – no).

P_t – current consumption of resources (e.g. energy, technical, human) at time t .

P_{max} – the maximum allowable load on the system at any given time.

T – the set of all possible moments in time.

This constraint ensures that the total resource usage at any time t does not exceed the allowable level P_{max} . For each time t , the total resource consumption of the tasks being performed at that time is determined. Some tasks are transferred to another time if the sum of all active tasks and their resource consumption exceeds the P_{max} limit. This avoids resource overload and ensures stable system operation.

The budget constraint determines that the cost of forming and operating a hybrid team in the maritime industry should not exceed a set limit [10]. This guarantees the efficient use of financial resources, allowing a balance between management quality and economic feasibility (4).

$$\sum_{e \in E} \sum_{t \in T} C_{e,t} x_{e,t} \leq B_{max} \quad (4)$$

where $C_{e,t}$ – costs of performing task e at time t (may include labour, equipment use, communication costs, etc.);

$x_{e,t}$ – binary variable which determines whether task e is being performed at time t (1 – yes, 0 – no);

B_{max} – maximum allowable budget for all team operations;

E – set of all possible tasks;

T – set of all moments in time.

The sum of all costs for performing tasks within the team should not exceed the maximum budget B_{max} .

In the maritime industry, regulated working time standards determine the maximum number of hours members of a hybrid team can work during a day, week or month. This restriction aims to prevent fatigue and improve occupational safety and compliance with international standards, particularly the Maritime Labour Convention (MLC 2006) and SOLAS. This restriction is expressed by formula (5):

$$\sum_{t \in T} x_{e,t} h_{e,t} \leq H_{max}, \forall e \in E \quad (5)$$

where $h_{e,t}$ – working time spent by a team member on task e at time t ;

$x_{e,t}$ – binary variable which determines whether task e is being performed at time t (1 – yes, 0 – no);

H_{max} – maximum allowable working hours for each team member over a given period (e.g. 14 hours per day or 72 hours per week);

E – set of all possible tasks;

T – set of all moments in time.

The sum of the hours worked by team members should not exceed the set limit H_{max} .

Managing hybrid teams in the maritime industry requires a precise distribution of tasks according to each team member's qualifications, experience and competencies [11]. The performance of certain operations (e.g. navigation, vessel maintenance, logistics management) is possible only by specialists with the appropriate skills. This limitation can be expressed using formula (6):

$$x_{e,t} * C_e \leq C_p, \forall e \in E, \forall p \in P \quad (6)$$

where $x_{e,t}$ – binary variable which determines whether task e is being performed at time t (1 – yes, 0 – no);

C_e – the level of competence required to perform task e ;

C_p – the level of competence of personnel p performing the task.

E – set of all possible tasks;

P – set of all team members.

Each task e can only be performed by a team member whose competencies C_p equal or exceed requirements C_e . Constraints on the compliance of competencies are essential in forming a hybrid team in the maritime industry. It ensures the correct distribution of tasks among team members, compliance with professional standards and certifications, minimising the risks associated with incompetent task performance, and effective use of the Agile methodology through the distribution of roles according to skills.

Thus, this model for optimising the process of forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry provides flexible management of human resources and tasks by

the principles of Agile. It allows us to balance key performance indicators (KPIs), task performance costs, risk level, and team workload, ensuring optimal resource allocation in a dynamic maritime environment. Process optimisation occurs by maximising the overall efficiency of the team's work, taking into account the constraints. This allows adaptability to changing conditions, minimises operational risks, and improves coordination between onboard, shore-based, and remote personnel.

Conclusions. The proposed model for forming hybrid teams in the maritime industry based on the Agile methodology allows for effectively organising work processes in a dynamic shipping environment. It considers the peculiarities of interaction between onboard, shore-based and remote personnel, ensures a clear division of roles, implements flexible communication mechanisms and increases the adaptability of teams to changes. Using the Agile methodology optimises project management processes, reduces risks associated with technical malfunctions, communication barriers, and human factors, and improves coordination between all participants in maritime operations. The developed mathematical model allows for formalising the decision-making process when forming hybrid teams, considering budget constraints, time frames, level of personnel competence, weather conditions and port congestion. It ensures maximum efficiency of resource allocation and allows for flexible adaptation of the team's work depending on changes in the external environment. The optimisation approach guarantees increased productivity, cost reduction and minimisation of downtime in shipping processes. At the same time, the effective implementation of this model requires overcoming several challenges, including ensuring stable communication between all team members, forming an Agile culture among maritime personnel, and integrating digital technologies into traditional management methods. Further research can be aimed at expanding the mathematical model to predict potential risks and developing practical cases for its implementation in maritime companies.

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